

Molecular Adsorption and Ion-Exchange of Weak Organic Electrolytes on Ion-Exchange Resin

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The molecular adsorptions of some carboxylic fatty acids, as well as chloro-substituted acetic acids together with hydrochloric acid on the Cation-exchange resin, Amberlite-IR-120 in its hydrogen form have been studied. It has been found that the adsorption increases in the order, hydrochloric < formic < acetic < n-propionic < monochloroacetic < n-butyric < dichloroacetic < trichloroacetic. Also with the same ion-exchange resin, the simultaneous ion-exchange as well as molecular adsorptions of liberated acids from solutions of sodium, potassium and magnesium salts of carboxylic acids have been investigated and the results computed.

THE ion-exchange properties of synthetic ion-exchange resins from solutions of electrolytes containing counter-ions different from that in the resins, have been extensively studied^{1,2,3,4}. The resins also possess the property of adsorbing non-electrolytes and electrolytes molecularly from their solutions^{5,6,7,8}. In cases of weak electrolytes like the aliphatic carboxylic acids, both ion-exchange and molecular adsorption take place simultaneously. Though in these cases, ion-exchange and adsorption have been investigated but rarely differentiation has been made between the two. Starobinets and Gleim⁹ studied the ion-exchange and adsorption of aliphatic carboxylic acids on anion-exchange resins in their halide forms and it is they who first differentiated between ion-exchange and molecular adsorption.

When a solution of an aliphatic carboxylic acid is equilibrated with the hydrogen form of a cation exchanger, there will be no ion-exchange but the acid will be molecularly adsorbed on the resin. But when a solution of a salt of an aliphatic carboxylic acid is equilibrated with the hydrogen form of a cation-exchanger, the hydrogen ion in the exchanger will of course, be exchanged with the counter-ion in the salt solution and an equivalent amount of a free acid will, be formed in the solution but a part of the free acid will be molecularly adsorbed on the resin.

This paper presents the results of investigation of pure molecular adsorption of hydrochloric acid, straight chain aliphatic acids ranging from formic to n-butyric acids as well as three chlorosubstituted acetic acids on the hydrogen form of a cation-exchanger. An attempt has also been made in this paper to differentiate between molecular adsorption and ion-exchange by using solutions of sodium, potassium and magnesium salts of

formic to n-butyric acids with the same cation exchanger. In all these cases Amberlite-IR-120 (PSSA with 8% DVB) in the hydrogen form was used.

Experimental

The strongly acidic cation-exchanger, Amberlite-IR-120 with a nominal content of 8% divinyl benzene was conditioned first by converting the commercial resin into sodium form with about 1N sodium hydroxide and then reconverting the resin into its hydrogen form by treatment with about 2N HCl. In between these processes the material was washed thoroughly with water. The resin in its hydrogen form was finally washed by passing double distilled water through the column containing resin until the resin was free from any foreign ion. This was checked by pH measurement of the washed water. The resin was then dried in air and kept in a closed container. The exchange capacity, and the moisture content of the moist resin were then determined. The exchange capacity in the H-form resin was (4.91 ± 0.04) meq/gm, dry resin for the different lots.

The aliphatic carboxylic acids ranging from formic to n-butyric as well as the three chloro-substituted acetic acids and the hydrochloric acid, were all "analar grades" and used without any purification. About 2 gms. of the air-dried resin (of known moisture contents) were taken in bottles with ground glass stoppers into which 50 ml of acid solutions of known concentrations were added. The mixtures were shaken for 4 hours and then kept for 48 hours to ensure attainment of equilibrium. The final concentrations of the equilibrated acid solutions were determined and from the difference between the initial and final concentrations, the adsorptions of acids per gm of dry resin

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were calculated. The concentrations of the acids were found out by alkalimetric titration using phenolphthalein as indicator.

Sodium formate, acetate and n-propionate of "analar grade" were used without purification. But sodium salt of n-butyric acid was prepared by adding analar sodium carbonate into the corresponding "analar" acid. The acid was taken in slight excess. The solution containing the sodium salt was then evaporated to dryness, washed carefully with double distilled water and finally recrystallised from water. The potassium salt solutions of the aliphatic carboxylic acids were prepared by adding equal volumes of equinormal solutions of potassium hydroxide to the corresponding acids. The concentrations of sodium and potassium salt solutions were determined by conductometric titrations with standard hydrochloric acid.

The magnesium salt solutions were prepared by adding "analar" magnesium oxide in slight excess to the corresponding acids and then filtering out the solutions. The concentrations of the magnesium salt solutions were determined by titrating with standard EDTA solutions using Eriochrome Black-T indicator.

As in the determination of adsorption, 50 ml of salt solutions of different concentrations were added to about 2 gms. of air-dried resin (of known moisture content) and allowed to attain equilibrium as before. The final concentrations of salt solutions were determined in aliquots by conductometric titrations in the cases of sodium and potassium salts and EDTA titration in the case of magnesium salts. From the difference between initial and final concentrations of salt solutions, the ion-exchanges per gm of dry resin were calculated by the formula,

$$\text{Exchange} = \frac{(C_i - C_e) \times 100}{(100 - W) \times W_R} \times V \text{ meq/g dry resin} \quad (1)$$

Where, C_i = initial conc. of salt solution in eqv. per litre.

W_R = weight of resin in gms.

W = water content in weight per cent.

V = solution volume in ml.

C_e = equilibrium conc. of salt solution in eqv. per litre

The concentrations of the liberated acids were determined in the separate aliquots by alkalimetric titration. These acid concentrations were subtracted from the differences between initial and final concentrations of the salt solutions. From the subtracted values the adsorptions of liberated carboxylic acids per gm of dry

resin were calculated as,

Adsorption of

$$\text{liberated acid} = \frac{[(C_i - C_e) - C_A] \times 100 \times V}{(100 - W) \times W_R} \text{ meq/g. dry resin} \quad (2)$$

where, C_A = Conc. of liberated acid in eqv./litre.

Before doing these experiments the analytical methods employed were tested with salt solutions of known concentrations as well as mixtures of salt solutions and carboxylic acids of known concentrations. The results were found to be satisfactory within experimental error.

To see whether a salt of a carboxylic acid is adsorbed by the same salt form of the resin, experiments were performed with sodium form of the resin and sodium acetate solutions of different concentrations. It was found, within experimental error, that no adsorption takes place in these cases.

All these experiments were performed in room temperatures ($30 \pm 2^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

The experimental adsorption isotherms of carboxylic acids (formic to n-butyric), as well as, those of mono-, di- and trichloroacetic acids on the cation-exchange resin, Amberlite-IR-120, in its hydrogen form are presented in fig 1. For comparison, the isotherm for hydrochloric acid have also been included in this figure.

Fig. 1. Adsorption Isotherms of Carboxylic Acids on the hydrogen form of Amberlite-IR-120.

1. Formic, 2. Acetic, 3. Propionic, 4. n-butyric, 5. monochloro-acetic, 6. dichloro-acetic, 7. trichloro-acetic, 8. Hydrochloric.

The adsorption results for formic, acetic, propionic and n-butyric acids are in agreement with those found by Bhatnagar et al⁵, Reichenberg & Wall⁷, and Starobinets & Kharevich¹¹. The adsorption increases with the chainlength of the carboxylic acids, i.e.; formic < acetic < propionic < n-butyric. Reichenberg and Wall⁷ explained their results from the standpoint of London dispersion interactions between the hydrocarbon part of the adsorbate molecules and benzene nuclei of the resin. The interaction and hence the adsorption increase with increasing chainlength of the carboxylic acids. Schneider, Kresheck and Scheraga¹⁰ from their studies on the thermodynamic parameters, e.g.; standard free energy, enthalpy and entropy of the interactions between the carboxylic acids and a hydrocarbon network of polystyrene, concluded that the molecular adsorption should increase with the chainlengths of the carboxylic acids, by a mechanism involving hydrophobic effect and consequent decrease in the structure of water. Starobinets and Kharevich¹¹ measured the adsorption of aliphatic monocarboxylic acids on a cation-exchange resin in the absence of ion-exchange process. Their results also indicate an increase in adsorption with the number of -CH₂ groups in the acids. They also invoked the hydrophobic bond formation to explain their results.

The adsorption of the strong acid, HCl, is very small as shown in figure 1. From the results of the experiments with the sodium form of the resin with sodium acetate solutions with concentrations from 1.5M to 0.3M, it has been seen that the amount of acetate ion adsorbed is zero within experimental error. This shows that the undissociated form of the carboxylic acids is only adsorbed. The same conclusion was reached by Schneider et al¹⁰ who used sodium butyrate solution. The adsorption of carboxylic fatty acids is, therefore, expected to be a function of both the chainlength and dissociation constant. Carboxylic acids having higher dissociation constants should be less adsorbed by the resin. The dissociation constants¹² of the carboxylic acids used, decreases in the order, formic (1.77×10^{-4}) > acetic (1.77×10^{-5}) > n-butyric (1.54×10^{-5}) > propionic (1.34×10^{-5}). Although the dissociation constant of n-butyric acid is slightly greater than that of propionic acid, it is more strongly adsorbed than the latter. Of the two opposing effects, the chainlength and dissociation constant, the effect of the dissociation constant is possibly more than compensated by the effect of chainlength in the case of n-butyric acid.

To examine the effect of dissociation constants on the adsorption, the adsorption of chloro-substituted acetic acids on the same cation-exchange resin has been studied. In these acids, the chain-length may be assumed to remain same as in acetic acid whereas the dissociation constant¹² increases considerably with the number of chlorine atoms in the acids. So it is to be expected that the order of adsorption would be, acetic > monochloroacetic > dichloroacetic > trichloroacetic. But actually just the opposite order has been found: acetic < monochloroacetic < dichloroacetic < trichloroacetic. It is quite unlikely that the chloro-substituted acetic acids have higher hydrophobicity than that of acetic acid. So it seems

that the mechanism of adsorption in these cases is somewhat complicated. There may be some kind of interaction between the chlorosubstituted group with the hydrocarbon matrix of the resin.

The results of the experiments on ion-exchange and simultaneous adsorptions of liberated free acids by the hydrogen form of the resin with the sodium, potassium and magnesium salts of carboxylic acids are shown in figures 2, 3 and 4 respectively. From the consideration of the dissociation constants¹² of the carboxylic acids,

Fig. 2. a) Ion-Exchanges of Sodium Carboxylates and b) Adsorptions of corresponding liberated acids on the hydrogen form of Amberlite-IR-120.

1. Sodium formate, 2. Sodium acetate, 3. Sodium propionate, 4. Sodium n-butyrate.

Fig. 3. a) Ion-Exchanges of Potassium carboxylates and b) Adsorptions of corresponding liberated acids on the hydrogen form of Amberlite-IR-120.

1. Potassium acetate, 2. Potassium Propionate, 3. Potassium n-butyrate.

Fig. 4. a) Ion Exchanges of Magnesium Carboxylates and b) Adsorptions of corresponding liberated acids on the hydrogen form of Amberlite-IR-120
 1. Magnesium formate, 2. Acetate, 3. Propionate, 4. n-butyrate.

it is expected that lower the dissociation constant, higher will be the exchange of the cation from the salt solutions. This is borne out in the cases of sodium and potassium salts in dilute solutions, e.g ; formate < acetate < n-butyrate < propionate. But at higher concentrations, the position of propionate and n-butyrate is reversed, e.g ; propionate < n-butyrate. Here also the effect of dissociation constant is overcome by the effect of chainlength of the butyrate ion in concentrated solution. The adsorption of the liberated acids runs parallel to the ion-exchange from the corresponding salt solutions : higher the ion-exchange, higher the adsorption ; the adsorption increases with increase in the chainlength of the carboxylic acid, as is found in the case of pure molecular adsorption of the carboxylic acids on the hydrogen form of the same cation-exchange resin.

The magnesium salt solutions of the carboxylic acids present a different picture. With increasing concentration of the salt solutions both the ion-exchange and adsorption of the liberated acids at first increase, then decrease and afterwards tend to increase very slowly showing a maxima in the curve (fig. 4). There is no regularity of ion-exchange or adsorption with the chainlength or dissociation constant of the carboxylic acids. This is possibly due to formation of complex between magnesium and carboxylate ions.

The behaviour of three different salts of the n-butyric acid are compared in fig. 5 ; with the salts of other acids same type of figures may be drawn. The results obtained from these figures are summarised in the table 1.

Fig. 5. a) Exchanges of Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} from their n-butyrate solutions and b) Simultaneous adsorptions of liberated n-butyric acids on the hydrogen form of Amberlite-IR-120.

1. Sodium n-butyrate, 2. Potassium n-butyrate, 3. Magnesium n-butyrate.

The selectivity of three ions (Na^+ , K^+ and Mg^{2+}) from all the different carboxylate salt solutions are in the order, $\text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Mg}^{2+}$ in dilute solutions. This is in conformity with the fact that ion-exchanger prefers the counter-ion of higher valence and larger size and the preference increases with dilution of the solution^{1,2}. The same order of selectivity of these cations over hydrogen from cation-exchange resins has been found by many earlier workers. In concentrated solutions, the position of the Mg^{2+} ion comes down

TABLE-1

Salt Solutions	Concentration	Selectivity of Ions	Adsorption of liberated acid from the salts
Acetate :	Dilute range :	$\text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Mg}^{2+}$	$\text{Na} \approx \text{K} < \text{Mg}$
	Conc. range :	$\text{Na}^+ < \text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{K}^+$	$\text{Mg} < \text{Na} < \text{K}$
Propionate :	Dilute range :	$\text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Mg}^{2+}$	$\text{K} < \text{Na} < \text{Mg}$
	Conc. range :	$\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+$	$\text{Mg} < \text{K} < \text{Na}$
n-butyrate :	Dilute range :	$\text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Mg}^{2+}$	$\text{K} < \text{Mg} < \text{Na}$
	Conc. range :	$\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+$	$\text{Mg} < \text{K} < \text{Na}$

due to the formation of complex, as mentioned earlier. As regards the adsorption of liberated acids in the case of acetate solutions, more acid is adsorbed from potassium salt than from sodium one. But from propionate and n-butyrate salt solutions, their position is reversed, adsorption of acid is greater from sodium salts than from potassium salts. The behaviour of magnesium salts again is different in dilute and in concentrated solutions due to the same reason as mentioned already.

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